

TOWARDS THE APPROACH TO DATABASE STRUCTURE GENERATION FROM
BUSINESS RULES BASED ON NATURAL LANGUAGE EXPRESSIONS

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Abstract. *This paper presents the approach to the database structure design using the translation from business rules based on natural language expression written in English language into SQL scripts. Business rules are translated into database tables, columns, and relations based on foreign keys. A software prototype of business rules translation into SQL statements is described, as well as its usage example is considered.*

Introduction. Appearance of customer-centric software development practices, such as Martin's RAD (Rapid Application Development) and then Agile has allowed not only satisfying customer's requirements, but providing early deliveries of the product [1]. Since databases are baselines for almost all applications, the success of early database delivery is vital for the product delivery in general.

According to Wiegers and Beatty [2], a business rule is a statement that defines or constraints some aspect of the business. There are five kinds of business rules (facts, constraints, action enablers, inferences, and computations), among which facts are used to describe associations or relations between important business terms, and are important for data entities that might appear in data models [2].

Facts business rules are used to define database static structure in terms of entities (tables), attributes (columns), and relations (foreign keys). Hence, the goal of this research is to improve the process of database design at its early stages, by translating business rules into executable SQL (Structured Query Language) statements in order to obtain working database prototype faster and directly from captured facts.

Methodology. In this paper we have studied translation of business rules written in a natural English language (or at least close enough to it) into the executable SQL statements for database deployment on the DBMS (Database Management System) server.

The syntax of business rules, which define entities and relations between the entities, can be described using the extended Backus-Naur form (BNF):

$$\langle \textit{relation_business_rule} \rangle ::= \{ \textit{each} \mid \textit{some} \} \langle \textit{parent_entity} \rangle \\ \{ \textit{is} \langle \textit{relation} \rangle \} \{ \textit{one} \mid \textit{many} \} \langle \textit{child_entity} \rangle$$

Therefore, the following regular expression could be proposed in order to parse facts business rules, which define entities and relations between the entities, according to the described BNF syntax:

$$RX_{Fact} = "(each|some)\s + (.+)\s + ((is).+)\s + (one|many)\s + (.+)"$$

This regular expression assumes that tokens of the business rule should be separated by at least one space. Tokens extracted using the regular expression RX_{Fact} are trimmed, single spaces or sequences of spaces are replaced with underscores. Plural entity identifiers are singularized.

The syntax of business rules, which define entities and their attributes, can be described using the extended BNF as well:

$$\langle \textit{entity_business_rule} \rangle ::= \{ \textit{each} \} \langle \textit{entity} \rangle \\ \{ \textit{has} \} \{ \langle \textit{attribute} \rangle, \dots \}$$

Therefore, the following regular expression could be proposed in order to parse facts business rules, which define entities and their attributes, according to the described BNF syntax:

$$RX_{Def} = "(each)\s + (.+)(has)\s + (.+)"$$

This regular expression also assumes that tokens of the business rule should be separated by at least one space. Attributes introduced in the last token of the regular expression RX_{Def} should be separated by commas in order to be recognized and processed correctly (splitted by a comma). Tokens extracted using the regular expression RX_{Def} are trimmed, single spaces or sequences of spaces are replaced with underscores.

Considered regular expressions RX_{Fact} and RX_{Def} allow getting the tokens that could be transformed into elementary SQL statements of the DDL (Data Definition Language) sublanguage using the following metamodel (see Fig. 1).

According to the proposed procedure, tokens, obtained as the results of business rules parsing using the introduced regular expressions RX_{Fact} and RX_{Def} , are then transformed into CREATE TABLE and ALTER TABLE expressions of SQL language; ordered in the correct way (in order to avoid the situation when the table, which corresponding CREATE TABLE has not executed yet, is tried to be altered); and executed by the relational database server. For the experiments we have chosen MariaDB database server.

Figure 1 – Parsed business rules metamodel

For now, at the early stage of this research, the data types of attributes are by default considered as VARCHAR (255), except primary attributes. When mapping the relational model into the DDL statements, the primary keys should be implemented as auto incremented INTEGER columns in order to simplify their processing in a database. Obviously the primary attributes are all should have the “not null” property, as well as the foreign key attributes in order to provide the strong relational integrity. Auto-increment keys and not null fields are the essentials of relational databases supported by all well-known DBMS. By default primary keys, as well as corresponding foreign keys, are all artificial (entity name concatenated with “_id” suffix).

The general sequence of business rules translation into SQL statements is presented in Fig. 2.

Figure 2 – Business rules into SQL statements translation sequence

Proposed software architecture of the experimental stage is demonstrated in Fig. 3.

Figure 3 – Experimental stage software architecture

Fully-functioning web application is free and accessible by the corresponding link [3].

Results. As the example we have used the following text as the input. It outlines business rules, which define entities, attributes, and relations, for the products supply domain:

“Each supplier has address, email, phone. Some supplier is described as one person. Some supplier is described as one company. Each person has first name, last name, ssn. Each company has name, contact person, bank account. Each product has sku, title, amount, price, discount. Each supplier is assigned to many contracts. Each contract is assigned to many products. Each contract has number, date, comment.”

User interface of the developed software prototype is shown in Fig. 4.

Figure 4 – User interface of the developed software prototype

Obtained SQL statements (Fig. 4), to which given business rules were translated, were passed to the MariaDB server and successfully executed. The schema of generated database structure is shown in Fig. 5.

Figure 5 – Deployed database structure

This schema (Fig. 5) fully corresponds to the given business rules that describe entities and relations according to considered products supply domain. Generated SQL statements are accessible at [3].

Conclusion. In this paper we have presented the approach to the rapid database design based on the translation of the business rules system based on the natural language expressions written in English language into DDL SQL scripts that can be further deployed to the DBMS server.

According to the proposed approach, business rules, which define entities, attributes, and relations, are translated into the code that defines database tables, columns, and relations based on foreign keys. The software prototype that implements business rules translation into DDL SQL statements is described, as well as its usage example is considered using the products supply domain.

Future work includes improvement of the user interface in order to enable building of facts from pre-defined terms, as well as development of a model for suggestion of data types based on columns names.

References.

[1] R. Stephens, *Beginning Software Engineering*. John Wiley & Sons, 2015.
 [2] K. Wiegers and J. Beatty, *Software Requirements*. 3rd ed. Pearson Education, 2013.
 [3] Available: br2sql, <https://github.com/br2sql/br2sql.github.io> [Accessed: September 15, 2020].